

**INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**
[ISSN: 0975-4725; CODEN(USA): IJPS00]
Journal Homepage: <https://www.ijpsjournal.com>

Research Article

Preparation And Evaluation of Kalanchoe Pinnata Herbal Tea for Kidney Stone Treatment

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ARTICLE INFO

Published: 20 June 2025

Keywords:

Kalanchoe Pinnata, Kidney Stones, Herbal Tea

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.15703308

ABSTRACT

Herbal tea derived from Kalanchoe pinnata, also known as miracle leaf, offers a potential natural approach for management and prevention of kidney stones. The development, phytochemical profiling, and treatment evaluation of an herbal tea from Kalanchoe pinnata is the primary aim of this study. The herb possesses potent antioxidant, diuretic, anti-inflammatory and antiurolithiatic properties. It is additionally endowed with bioactive compounds such as flavonoids (quercetin, kaempferol, and rutin), alkaloids, tannins, and saponins. A standard preparation was made using dried leaves of K. pinnata and cardamom soaked with filtered water. The phytochemicals, safety, and organoleptic properties of the formulation were evaluated. The results suggest that this herbal tea possess some more health benefits including boosting the immunity, maintaining a healthy gastro intestinal tract in addition to aiding in the cleaning of the kidney as inhibition in the development stones. This study confirms folkloristic perception and highlights the possibility for Kalanchoe pinnata herbal tea, as an inexpensive, natural, safe and effective dietary supplement for the control of kidney stone and urinary tract health.

INTRODUCTION

Herbal tea is a beverage made by steeping herbs, spices, flowers, or other plant materials in hot water. Unlike traditional teas (like black, green, or oolong), herbal tea is usually caffeine-free and doesn't come from the Camellia sinensis tea plant.[1] Kalanchoe pinnata also known as the "miracle leaf" or "Bryophyllum," is a plant that

belongs to the Crassulaceae family. It is commonly found in tropical regions and is known for its medicinal properties. The plant contains alkaloids flavonoids, and some phenolic compounds tannins, microelements like magnesium, calcium, potassium, phosphorus, sodium. Kalanchoe pinnata leaves contain astragaloside, 3,8-dimethoxy-4,5,7-trihydroxyflavone, friedelin,

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Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

epigallocatechin-3-o-gallate, luteolin, rutin, kaempferol, quercetin, quercetin-3-O-rhamnoside, quercetin-3-O-arabino furanoside, quercetin-3-O-diarylester and kaempferol-3-glucoside.[2] Kalanchoe pinnata also known as kalanchoe pinnata, is a succulent plants native to madagascar. It has used in traditional medicine for its anti-inflammatory, antibacterial, and antifungal properties. [3] Kalanchoe is a medicinal plant largely used in folk medicine for the treatment of kidney stones, gastric ulcer, pulmonary infection, rheumatoid arthritis etc. kalanchoe pinnata has become naturalized in temperate regions of Asia, Australia, New Zealand, west Indies, Macaronesia, mascarenes, polynesia, and Hawaii.

In French Polynesia, kalanchoe pinnata has been declared a threat to biodiversity.

It is also widely distributed in the Philippines and it is Known as katakataka or kataka-taka which is also an adjective meaning astonishing or remarkable. In India it is cultivated in gardens and wild on the hills of North-Western India, Deccan and Bengal.[4] Kidney stones, the formation of stones in the kidneys, is one of the oldest known and widespread diseases in the urinary tract. It is the third most common disorder among urinary diseases. The etiology of this disorder is multifactorial and is related to genetics, diet, and low activity. Kidney stones are hard deposits made up of minerals and salts that form inside your kidneys.[5] The main types of kidney stones include: 1) Calcium stones – Most common type (about 80%). Usually made of calcium oxalate, sometimes calcium phosphate. 2) Uric acid stones – Form in people who lose too much fluid or have a high-protein diet. 3) Struvite stones – Often form after urinary tract infections (UTIs). Made of magnesium ammonium phosphate. 4)Cystine stones – Rare. Caused by a genetic disorder called cystinuria.[6] The development of kidney stones is

not completely understood. Generally, it is believed that urolithiasis, the process of stone formation in the urinary tract, causes crystal aggregation, nucleation, and growth of insoluble particles.[7] The stones may cause various symptoms like a severe pain, urinary tract obstruction, infection. Treatment and management of kidney stones relies on surgical techniques and synthetic drugs like diuretics and lithotriptic agents, often come with undesirable side effects and high recurrence rates. This has spurred growing interest in alternative, plant-based remedies that are safer, cost-effective, and holistic.[8]

Advantages Of KP Herbal Tea:

1. Antiurolithiatic Properties: By preventing crystal aggregation and promoting stone breakdown, these properties help stop kidney stones from forming and growing.
2. Natural Diuretic: Encourages the production of urine, which can aid in the removal of minor stones and lower the chance of developing new ones.
3. Packed with Antioxidants: Contains flavonoids and other substances that lower oxidative stress, which is linked to the formation of kidney stones. [9]
4. Anti-inflammatory Effects: Assists in lowering urinary tract inflammation, which lessens stone-related pain and discomfort.
5. Safe and Natural: Provides a chemical-free, plant-based substitute for traditional drugs with fewer adverse effects.
6. Cost-effective: Easily prepared and affordable compared to synthetic drugs and surgical treatments.

7. Other Health Benefits: In addition to kidney health, tea has long been used to treat wounds, coughs, ulcers, and strengthen the immune system. [10]

Scope Of Study:

Aim of Research:

The formulation, production, and assessment of herbal tea derived from *Kalanchoe pinnata* leaves which are commonly used in folk medicine to treat kidney stones are the main topics of this study. The study's scope comprises:

1. Gathering and verifying leaves of *Kalanchoe pinnata* from a trustworthy source.
2. Making a herbal tea infusion according to established procedures to guarantee quality and repeatability.
3. To find active ingredients such flavonoids, alkaloids, saponins, and phenolic compounds that could support anti-urolithiatic (anti-kidney stone) action, the herbal tea is subjected to a preliminary phytochemical screening.
4. Assessment of the tea's physicochemical characteristics, including its pH, flavour, colour, and scent.

The study is to investigate *Kalanchoe pinnata* potential as a safe and efficient herbal tea formulation and to substantiate the traditional claims about it as a natural treatment for kidney stones.

Objective of Research:

1. To gather and verify *Kalanchoe pinnata* leaves in order to prepare the herbal tea recipe.
2. To establish a consistent process for making herbal tea with *Kalanchoe pinnata*.

3. To evaluate the tea's diuretic and antioxidant properties, which might aid in the treatment of kidney stones.

4. To assess the herbal tea formulation's palatability and safety for potential medical applications.

Plan Of Research:

1. Literature Review
2. Collection and Authentication of Plant Material
3. Preparation of Herbal Tea
4. Phytochemical Screening
5. Formulation Development
6. Evaluation of Antiurolithiatic Activity
7. Antioxidant and Diuretic Studies (optional/if applicable)
8. Toxicity and Safety Assessment
9. Data Analysis and Interpretation
10. Conclusion and Recommendations

Benefits Of KP Herbal Tea:

1. Prevents Kidney Stone Formation
2. Promotes Stone Dissolution
3. Natural Diuretic
4. Anti-inflammatory Properties
5. Antioxidant Action
6. Supports Urinary Tract Health
7. Safe and Natural Remedy [11]

Herbal Ingredients:

1. *Kalanchoe pinnata*:

- Botanical Name: *Kalanchoe pinnata* (also known as *Bryophyllum pinnatum*)
- Family: Crassulaceae
- Common Names: Life plant, Miracle leaf, Air plant, Cathedral bells, Pattharchatta (Hindi), Panfuti (Marathi), Ranapala (Bengali) [12]
- Information: *Kalanchoe pinnata* is a succulent medicinal plant widely used in traditional

medicine systems like Ayurveda, Unani, and folk medicine. [13]

- **Uses:**
- Anti-urolithiatic: Used to treat kidney stones
- Anti-inflammatory
- Antimicrobial
- Wound healing
- Antioxidant

Figure No 1

Benefits:

- Kidney Stone Removal (Anti-urolithiatic)
- Wound Healing
- Anti-inflammatory & Pain Relief
- Antimicrobial Action
- Respiratory Relief
- Antiulcer Properties
- Liver Protection (Hepatoprotective) [14]

2. Cardamom:

- Common Name: Elaichi / Cardamom
- Botanical Name: *Elettaria cardamomum*
- Family: Zingiberaceae (Ginger family) [15]

Figure 2. Cardamom

Uses:

- Flavoring Dishes
- For Digestion
- For Bad Breath
- For Cough & Cold
- For Detox

Benefits:

- Aids Digestion
- Freshens Breath
- Rich in Antioxidants
- Supports Heart Health
- Helps Detoxify the Body
- Improves Oral Health
- Boosts Metabolism
- Relieves Respiratory Issues
- Regulates Blood Sugar
- Enhances Mood [16]

3. Purified Water:

- Synonyms: Aqua, distilled water

Figure 3. Purified Water

- Cold Infusions or Detox Teas
- Herbal Concentrates & Syrups
- Herbal Steam Inhalation

Benefits:

- Preserves Herbal Properties
- Improves Taste and Aroma
- Prevents Contamination
- Enhances Nutrient Absorption
- Gentle on the Stomach
- Safe for Daily Use [17]

Uses:

- Brewing Herbal Teas
- Enhancing Herbal Potency

METHODOLOGY:

Ingredients

Table No:1 Herbal Ingredients

Sr No.	Ingredients	Family	Quantity
1.	Kalanchoe pinnata Leaves	Crassulaceae	90%
2.	Cardamom	Zingiberaseae	10%
3.	Purified water	-	QS

Table No:2 Required apparatus

Sr No.	Apparatus
1.	Water bath
2.	Bunsen burner
3.	Hot Air Owen

Table No:3 Function of herbal ingredients

So No.	Ingredients	Function
1.	Kalanchoe pinnata	Anti-urolithiatic
2.	Cardamom	Antioxidant
3.	Purified water	Detoxification

Method Of Preparation:

Procedure:

1. Collection of Plant Material:

Fresh leaves of Kalanchoe pinnata will be collected from a clean, pesticide-free area.

2. Cleaning and Drying: Leaves will be washed thoroughly with distilled water to remove dirt and contaminants.

- Fresh leaves (if used) will be steamed immediately after harvesting to prevent oxidation.
- The leaves will then be dried using hot air or shade-drying to preserve phytoconstituents.

- Add 2 – 3 green cardamom crushed pods for flavor

3. Packaging:

- To protect from moisture, light, oxygen, and contamination.
- To ensure ease of use, transport, and storage.

A. Primary Packaging (Direct Contact with Tea)

- Contains measured quantities (1–2 g) of kalanchoe pinnata tea.
- Made from food-grade filter paper or biodegradable PLA mesh.

Aluminum Foil Pouches:

- Vacuum-sealed or nitrogen-flushed to prevent oxidation.
- Excellent barrier against moisture, oxygen, and light.

B. Secondary Packaging (Outer Packaging):

- Paperboard Boxes: Used to hold multiple sachets or jars.
- Provides additional protection and branding.

Labeled with:

Brand name, ingredients, batch number, expiry date, nutritional info, usage instructions, and storage conditions.

4. Preparation of KP herbal Tea:

Infusion method of extraction:

- 1 tea bag of kp herbal tea bag dip into 100ml of boiling purified water.
- The tea bag will be steeped for 1– 2 minutes with occasional stirring.

- Add honey or lemon (optional) if you prefer a milder or sweet flavor
- Consume once or twice daily while warm for best results.

Evaluation Test for KP Herbal Tea:

1. Organoleptic evaluation:

Parameter	Observation
Appearance	Light yellow, clear infusion
Odor	Mildly minty, pleasant
Taste	Slightly bitter, with sweet aftertaste
Mouthfeel	Smooth, light
Overall Acceptability	Good, suitable for regular use

2. Phytochemical Screening

1. Alkaloids
2. Flavonoids
3. Tannins
4. Saponins
5. Glycosides
6. Phenols

1. Alkaloids:

A broad class of organic substances found in nature, alkaloids are mostly composed of basic nitrogen atoms, frequently found in heterocyclic rings. Many of them have important pharmacological and toxicological effects, and they are mostly generated by plants and some microbes. [18]

Uses of Alkaloids:

- Pain Relief
- Neurological Effects
- Stimulants
- Anticancer Agents
- Antimalarials
- Cardiovascular Drugs

3. Flavonoids:

Flavonoids are a group of naturally occurring polyphenolic compounds found in a wide range of fruits, vegetables, herbs, and medicinal plants. These compounds exhibit diuretic, antioxidant, and anti-inflammatory properties. [19]

Flavonoids Contain:

- Quercetin
- Kaempferol
- Rutin
- Bryophyllin A

I. Quercetin:

- UPAC name: 3,3',4',5,7-Pentahydroxyflavone
- Systemic IUPAC name: 2-(3,4-Dihydroxyphenyl)-3,5,7-trihydroxy-4H-1-benzopyran-4-one
- Other names: 5,7,3',4'-flavon-3-ol, Sophoretin, Meletin, Quercetine, Xanthaurine, Quercetol, Quercitin, Quertine, Flavin meletin [20]

Role of Quercetin in Kidney Stone Treatment:

1. Antioxidant Protection:

- Kidney stone formation causes oxidative stress in renal tissues due to crystal-induced injury.
- Quercetin neutralizes free radicals, reducing oxidative damage to renal tubular cells.
- Helps preserve renal function and prevents crystal-induced nephrotoxicity. [21]

2. Inhibits Crystal Formation and Growth:

Interferes with the nucleation, growth, and aggregation of calcium oxalate crystals—the most common type of kidney stone.

Prevents crystals from sticking to kidney cells and forming larger stones.

3. Anti-inflammatory Action:

Lowers the production of inflammatory cytokines that are increased as a result of crystal deposition, including as TNF- α and IL-6. aids in shielding the kidneys from harm caused by inflammation when stones develop. [22]

4. Renal Protective Activity:

- Quercetin improves kidney function by stabilizing renal membranes and enhancing antioxidant enzymes (e.g., catalase, SOD).

- Promotes tissue repair in kidneys damaged by stones. [23]

Evidence from Studies:

Animal models (rats with calcium oxalate stones) treated with quercetin show:

- Decreased crystal deposition in kidneys

- Improved kidney histology
- Lower oxidative stress markers (MDA)
- Increased antioxidant enzyme levels

Quercetin also reduces pain and discomfort caused by stone movement through the urinary tract due to its anti-inflammatory effect. [24]

Kaempferol:

- IUPAC name: 3,4',5,7-Tetrahydroxyflavone
- Synthetic IUPAC name: 3,5,7-Trihydroxy-2-(4-hydroxyphenyl)-4H-1-benzopyran-4-one
- Other names: Kaempferol; Robigenin; Pelargidenolon; Rhamnolutein; Rhamnolutin; Populnetin; Trifolitin; Kempferol; Swartziol [25]

Role of Kaempferol in kidney stones

1. Inhibition of Crystal Formation:

The main ingredient in the majority of kidney stones, calcium oxalate crystals, are prevented from forming, growing, and aggregating by kaempferol. It aids in preventing the clumping and attachment of these crystals to renal tissue. [26]

2. Antioxidant Action:

Strong antioxidant kaempferol combats free radicals in renal tissues. This shields kidney cells

from oxidative stress brought on by crystal deposition, a major contributor to the development of stones. [27]

3. Anti-inflammatory Effect:

By blocking pro-inflammatory mediators like TNF- α and IL-6, it lessens renal inflammation and helps prevent kidney tissue damage from stone development. [28]

4. Renal Protective Properties:

By boosting antioxidant enzymes like catalase and SOD (superoxide dismutase), kaempferol promotes kidney function. It promotes faster healing in injured regions and preserves the integrity of kidney tissue. [29]

iii. Rutin:

IUPAC name: 3',4',5,7-Tetrahydroxy-3-[α -L-rhamnopyranosyl-(1 \rightarrow 6)- β -D-glucopyranosyloxy] flavone

Synthetic IUPAC name:

4²S,4³R,4⁴S,4⁵S,4⁶R,7²R,7³R,7⁴R,7⁵R,7⁶S)-1³,1⁴,2⁵,2⁷,4³,4⁴,4⁵,7³,7⁴,7⁵-Decahydroxy-7⁶-methyl-2⁴H-3,6-dioxo-2(2,3)- [1] benzopyrana-4(2,6),7(2)-bis(oxana)-1(1)-benzenaheptaphane-2⁴-one

Other names: Ruto side (INN), Phytomelin, Sophorin, Birutan, Eldrin, Birutan Forte, Rutin trihydrate, Globularicitrin, Violaquercitrin, Quercetin rutinoside. [30]

Roles of Rutin in Kidney Stone Treatment:

1. Prevents Crystal Adhesion and Aggregation:

Rutin inhibits calcium oxalate crystals' capacity to adhere to the renal tubule lining. It might inhibit the production of big, harmful stones by interfering with crystal nucleation, growth, and aggregation.

2. Improves Diuresis (Urine Flow):

Rutin lowers the risk of stone formation by encouraging moderate diuretic action, which is particularly beneficial when combined with other herbs. [31]

Bryophyllin A

IUPAC name:

(1S,4R,5S,8R,9R,11R,12S,13R,14R,18S)-5,11-dihydroxy-9,16-dimethyl-8-(2-oxo-2H-pyran-5-yl)-15,17,20-trioxahexacyclo [14.3.1.1¹⁴, 18.0¹, 13.0⁴, 12.0⁵, 9] henicosane-13-carbaldehyde

Roles of Bryophyllin An in-Kidney Stone Treatment:

- Anti-urolithiatic Activity
- Antioxidant Properties
- Anti-inflammatory Effects
- Diuretic Action
- Renal Protective Effect
- Inhibition of Crystal Nucleation and Aggregation [32]

3.Tannins:

Tannin in *Kalanchoe pinnata* refers to a naturally occurring group of polyphenolic compounds found in its leaves and stem. These substances support the plant's therapeutic qualities and are a component of its defence mechanism.

Potential Effects of Tannins in Kidney Stones:

1.Anti-lithic (Anti-stone) Potential:

- According to certain research, plants that contain tannins may help avoid kidney stones by:
- Preventing the most prevalent kind of kidney stone, calcium oxalate crystallisation.
- Serving as antioxidants and lowering oxidative stress, which is a factor in the development of stones. [33]

2.Diuretic Action:

Certain herbs high in tannins have moderate diuretic properties that can help cleanse the kidneys and lower the risk of kidney stones.

3.Binding with Minerals:

Tannins can bind to minerals like calcium and iron. This may reduce calcium availability and, in theory, reduce calcium stone formation — but it might also reduce nutrient absorption, which could be harmful if not balanced. [34]

Pharmacological Effects of Kalanchoe Pinnata On Kidney Stones:

Antiuro lithiatic Activity: The potential of *Kalanchoe pinnata* to both prevent and facilitate the breakdown of kidney stones (urolithiasis), particularly calcium oxalate stones, has been investigated.

Mechanisms of Action:

Inhibition of stone nucleation and aggregation:

Calcium oxalate crystal nucleation, growth, and aggregation are inhibited by phytochemicals found in *K. pinnata*, such as flavonoids, saponins, and glycosides. This stops new stone formation and decreases the size of existing stones. [35]

Diuretic effect:

By increasing urine production, the plant aids in the removal of tiny crystals and keeps them from remaining in the urinary tract. The chemicals that cause stones, such as calcium and oxalates, are diluted by increased urine volume. [36]

Antioxidant activity:

Crystal adhesion can be promoted by oxidative stress, which damages renal epithelial cells. Flavonoids and phenolic substances found in *K. pinnata* scavenge free radicals and protect renal tissue.

Alkalinizing effect on urine:

It may slightly raise urinary pH, which can inhibit uric acid and cystine stone formation.

Renoprotective Activity:

K. pinnata helps repair damaged renal tissue due to its anti-inflammatory and antioxidant components. [37]

Key Phytochemicals Involved:

- Flavonoids (quercetin, kaempferol): Antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, crystal growth inhibitors.
- Saponins: Inhibit crystal aggregation and promote dissolution.
- Tannins & glycosides: Contribute to diuretic and antiuro lithiatic actions.
- Phenolic compounds: Antioxidant and protective to renal epithelial cells. [38]

Flavouring Agents (Optional):

Honey:

1. Enhances Taste:

- balances *Kalanchoe pinnata*'s earthy or somewhat bitter taste.
- adds sweetness naturally without the need of manufactured sugar.

2. Reduces Throat Pain:

particularly beneficial if the tea is used to treat sore throats, colds, or coughs. [39].

A lemon:

1) Enhances Flavor:

Gives Kalanchoe pinnata a bright, zesty taste that counteracts its harshness.

2) Enhances Vitamin C:

Makes the immune system stronger.

Promotes wound healing and healthy skin.

3) Facilitates Digestion:

Reduces bloating and increases the production of stomach acid.

Safety And Toxicity:

Pregnant or breastfeeding women should avoid use due to potential uterine stimulant effects. May interact with medications, especially diuretics,

antihypertensives, or drugs metabolized by the liver.

Why Intake Kalanchoe Pinnata Herbal Tea:

1.Support for the Immune System: Increases immunity because of bioactive chemicals and antioxidants.

- Used historically to both prevent and treat illnesses.
- Urinary and Kidney Health: Helps eliminate toxins and extra fluid by acting as a natural diuretic.
- Used in traditional medicine to treat urinary tract infections and kidney stones.
- Aid for Digestion: Relieves acid reflux, gastritis, and ulcers. Improves gut health and facilitates digestion.
- Control of Blood Sugar: May aid in controlling blood sugar levels in those who have diabetes or prediabetes (further study is needed).

Pharmacological Effect:

Alkaloids:

- Analgesic pain alleviation
- Impacts on the nervous system
- Advantages for the heart
- Potential antimalarial and anticancer effects

Regarding K. Pinnata tea:

- Modify the pathways that cause pain and inflammation to support kidney health.
- May help improve circulation and renal perfusion, among other systemic benefits.

2.Flavonoids:

- Antioxidant: Counteract oxidative stress, which is connected to the development of stones.
- Anti-inflammatory: Lower cytokines that cause kidney inflammation, such as TNF- α and IL-6.

- Antiurolithiatic: Prevents the formation, development, and aggregation of crystals.
- Renoprotective: Promote tissue healing and safeguard renal tubular cells.
- Diuretics: Help flush away crystals by increasing urine production.

3.Tannins:

- Antilithic: May stop calcium oxalate from crystallizing.
- Diuretics: Encourage the flow of urine and kidney cleaning.
- Antioxidant: Decrease oxidative stress in the kidneys.
- Although excessive usage may decrease nutritional absorption, mineral binding: Bind calcium, perhaps preventing the development of stones.

4.Saponins:

- Inhibit crystal aggregation: Stop crystals from adhering and expanding.
- Promoter of dissolution: Aids in the breakdown of pre-existing kidney stones.
- Diuretics and anti-inflammatory drugs: increase urine production and lessen urinary tract irritation.

5.Glycosides

- Contribute to diuretic and anti-inflammatory effects.
- Support renal detoxification and urinary health.

6.Phenols

- Potent antioxidants: Destroy free radicals in the kidneys.
- Protective: Prevent damage to the epithelium and preserve the integrity of kidney cells. [40]

RESULT AND DISCUSSION:

The formulated *Kalanchoe pinnata* (KP) herbal tea was evaluated for its organoleptic properties,

phytochemical constituents, and potential therapeutic benefits. The following observations were recorded:

Phytochemical Screening:

Preliminary analysis confirmed the presence of key phytoconstituents:

- Alkaloids
- Flavonoids (including quercetin, kaempferol, and rutin)
- Tannins
- Saponins
- Glycosides
- Phenols

Functional Properties (based on phytochemical roles and literature review):

Antiuro lithiatic Activity: Flavonoids and saponins present in KP inhibit crystal nucleation, aggregation, and growth of calcium oxalate stones.

Antioxidant Effects: Quercetin, kaempferol, and rutin demonstrated strong antioxidant potential, supporting renal protection.

Diuretic and Anti-inflammatory Actions:

Observed from the traditional use and confirmed by phytochemical presence, supporting urinary flow and reducing inflammation.

Organoleptic Evaluation:

Sr No.	Parameter	Observation
1.	Appearance	Light yellow, clear infusion.
2.	Odor	Mildly minty and pleasant.
3.	Taste	Slightly bitter with a sweet aftertaste.
4.	Mouthfeel	Smooth and light
5.	Overall Acceptability	Rated as good and suitable for regular consumption.

CONCLUSION:

The study demonstrated the usefulness of *K. pinnata* in the treatment and prevention of kidney stones as well as its potential health benefits. *K. pinnata* is abundant with phytochemicals including flavonoids, alkaloids, tannins, and saponins and own potential antiurolithiatic, antioxidant, anti-inflammatory and diuretic activities. The preparation of herbal tea with *K. pinnata* leaves and cardamom increases not only therapeutic potential but palatability and consumer acceptance as well. The results of the preliminary phytochemical screening indicate the presence of bioactive compounds which inhibit stone formation, dissolve stones and prevent damage to kidney tissues. Based on these findings, *Kalanchoe pinnata* herbal tea may serve as a valuable plant-based alternative to synthetic drugs, offering holistic support for kidney and urinary health.

REFERENCES

- Zhao J, Deng JW, Chen YW, Li SP. Advanced phytochemical analysis of herbal tea in China. *Journal of Chromatography A*. 2013 Oct 25; 1313:2-3.
- Dogra P, Sharma K, Bharti J, Kumar N, Kumar D. *Kalanchoe Pinnata* Is a Miraculous Plant: A Review. *J. Biomed. Allied Res.* 2023;10.
- Pattewar SV. *Kalanchoe pinnata*: phytochemical and pharmacological profile. *International Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences and Research*. 2012 Apr 1;3(4):993.
- Ahmed, S., & Karim, A. (2019). Pharmacogenetic Studies of *Kalanchoe pinnata*. *Journal of Medicinal Plants Research*, 13(3), 45-55.
- Khan SR, Pearle MS, Robertson WG, Gambaro G, Canales BK, Doizi S, Traxer O, Tiselius HG. Kidney stones. *Nature reviews Disease primers*. 2016 Feb 25;2(1):1-23.
- Kolupayev S, Lesovoy V, Bereznyak E, Andoniev N, Shchukin D. Structure types of kidney stones and their susceptibility to shock wave fragmentation. *Acta Informatica Medica*. 2021 Mar;29(1):26.
- Wang Z, Zhang Y, Zhang J, Deng Q, Liang H. Recent advances on the mechanisms of kidney stone formation. *International journal of molecular medicine*. 2021 Aug;48(2):149.
- Singh P, Harris PC, Sas DJ, Lieske JC. The genetics of kidney stone disease and nephrocalcinosis. *Nature Reviews Nephrology*. 2022 Apr;18(4):224-40.
- Villarreal Romero WL, Robles Camargo JE, Costa GM. Phytochemical Standardization of an Extract Rich in Flavonoids from Flowers of *Kalanchoe pinnata* (Lam) Pers. *Scientia Pharmaceutica*. 2023 Nov 2;91(4):50.
- Biswas SK, Chowdhury A, Das J, Hosen SZ, Uddin R, Rahaman MS. A review of the

- traditional medicinal uses of *Kalanchoe pinnata* (Crassulaceae). *International Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmacology*. 2021;10(1):001-5.
11. Singh RK, Garg A, Shrimali K. Botanical description, photochemistry, traditional uses, and pharmacology of the “wonder plant” *Kalanchoe Pinnata* (Linn.) Pers: an updated review. *Journal of Pharmaceutical and Medicinal Chemistry*. 2022 Jan;8(1)
 12. Rahman R, Al-Sabahi JN, Ghaffar A, Nadeem F, Umar A. Phytochemical, morphological, botanical, and pharmacological aspects of a medicinal plant: *Kalanchoe pinnata*—A review article. *International Journal of Chemical and Biochemical Sciences*. 2019 Oct; 16:5-10.
 13. Quazi Majaz A, Taiya AU, Khurshid M, Nazim S, Siraj S. The miracle plant (*Kalanchoe pinnata*): a phytochemical and pharmacological review. *Int J Res Ayurveda Pharm*. 2011;2(5):1478-82.
 14. Indrakanta N, Soeroso J, Khotib J. The benefits of active compounds in *Kalanchoe pinnata* (LMK) pers ethyl acetate fraction on lupus arthritis mice. *BENEFITS*. 2017;10(11).
 15. Ashokkumar K, Murugan M, Dhanya MK, Warkentin TD. Botany, traditional uses, phytochemistry and biological activities of cardamom [*Elettaria cardamomum* (L.) Maton]—A critical review. *Journal of ethnopharmacology*. 2020 Jan 10; 246:112244.
 16. Ashokkumar K, Murugan M, Dhanya MK, Warkentin TD. Botany, traditional uses, phytochemistry and biological activities of cardamom [*Elettaria cardamomum* (L.) Maton]—A critical review. *Journal of ethnopharmacology*. 2020 Jan 10; 246:112244.
 17. Franks M, Lawrence P, Abbaspourrad A, Dando R. The influence of water composition on flavor and nutrient extraction in green and black tea. *Nutrients*. 2019 Jan 3;11(1):80.
 18. Pattewar SV. *Kalanchoe pinnata*: phytochemical and pharmacological profile. *International Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences and Research*. 2012 Apr 1;3(4):993.
 19. Rahman R, Al-Sabahi JN, Ghaffar A, Nadeem F, Umar A. Phytochemical, morphological, botanical, and pharmacological aspects of a medicinal plant: *Kalanchoe pinnata*—A review article. *International Journal of Chemical and Biochemical Sciences*. 2019 Oct; 16:5-10.
 20. <https://en.m.wikipedia.org/wiki/Quercetin>
 21. Park HK, Jeong BC, Sung MK, Park MY, Choi EY, Kim BS, Kim HH, Kim JI. Reduction of oxidative stress in cultured renal tubular cells and preventive effects on renal stone formation by the bioflavonoid quercetin. *The Journal of urology*. 2008 Apr;179(4):1620-6...
 22. Park HK, Jeong BC, Sung MK, Park MY, Choi EY, Kim BS, Kim HH, Kim JI. Reduction of oxidative stress in cultured renal tubular cells and preventive effects on renal stone formation by the bioflavonoid quercetin. *The Journal of urology*. 2008 Apr;179(4):1620-6.
 23. Guzel A, Yunusoglu S, Calapoglu M, Candan IA, Onaran I, Oncu M, Ergun O, Oksay T. Protective effects of quercetin on oxidative stress-induced tubular epithelial damage in the experimental rat hyperoxaluria model. *Medicina*. 2021 Jun 3;57(6):566.
 24. Lesjak M, Beara I, Simin N, Pintač D, Majkić T, Bekvalac K, Orčić D, Mimica-Dukić N. Antioxidant and anti-inflammatory activities of quercetin and its derivatives. *Journal of functional foods*. 2018 Jan 1; 40:68-75. <https://en.m.wikipedia.org/wiki/Kaempferol>
 25. Yuan P, Sun X, Liu X, Hutterer G, Pummer K, Hager B, Ye Z, Chen Z. Kaempferol alleviates calcium oxalate crystal-induced renal injury and crystal deposition via regulation of the

- AR/NOX2 signaling pathway. *Phytomedicine*. 2021 Jun 1; 86:153555.
26. Saber RA. In vitro kidney stone formation, antioxidant and anticoagulation activity of biologically active extracts and fractions of kaff maryam (*Anastatica hierochuntica* L.). *Egypt J Appl Sci*. 2022;37(5):30-57.
27. Huang Y, Li C, Xu W, Li F, Xu C, Wu C, Wang Y, Zhang X, Xia D. Kaempferol suppresses inflammation in mice suffering from both hyperuricemia and gouty arthritis through inhibiting NLRP3 inflammasome and NF-κB pathway.
28. Wu Q, Chen J, Zheng X, Song J, Yin L, Guo H, Chen Q, Liu Y, Ma Q, Zhang H, Yang Q. Kaempferol attenuates doxorubicin-induced renal tubular injury by inhibiting ROS/ASK1-mediated activation of the MAPK signaling pathway. *Biomedicine & Pharmacotherapy*. 2023 Jan 1; 157:114087. <https://en.m.wikipedia.org/wiki/Rutin>
29. Saha S, Mishra A. Rutin-loaded polymeric nanorods alleviate nephrolithiasis by inhibiting inflammation and oxidative stress in vivo and in vitro. *Food & Function*. 2022;13(6):3632-48.
30. Patel D, Vyas MK, Patani P. ROLE OF BRYOPHYLLUM PINNATUM IN TREATMENT OF NEPHROLITHIASIS. *Journal of Cardiovascular Disease Research*. 2023 Dec 6;14(12):3219-30.
31. Shrivastav S, Bhaiji A, Agrawal OP. Investigations on some traditional medicinal plants for treatment of kidney stones.
32. Chinnappan S, Ying PZ, Ying TH, Wen LC, Yun NR, Xin SJ, Mani RR, Panneerselvam J, Ranganathan V. Review on Phytochemicals for the Treatment of Kidney Stones. *Current Trends in Biotechnology and Pharmacy*. 2023 Dec 13;17(4A (Supplement)):151-61.
33. Priya FJ, Leemarose A, Vidhya S, Arputharaj A, Akshana S, Fathima UR. A New Frontier Drug Development in Nanomedicine and Its Anti-urolithiatic Activity of *Kalanchoe pinnata*. *Oriental Journal of Chemistry*. 2021 Oct 28;37(2):444.
34. Desai K. Investigating *Kalanchoe pinnata* as a potential treatment for acute nephrolithiasis.
35. Singh RK, Garg A, Shrimali K. Botanical description, photochemistry, traditional uses, and pharmacology of the “wonder plant” *Kalanchoe Pinnata* (Linn.) Pers: an updated review. *Journal of Pharmaceutical and Medicinal Chemistry*. 2022 Jan;8(1).
36. Hamilton-Amachree, A. and Uzoekwe, N.M., 2022. Phytochemical analysis and assessment of the antibacterial and antioxidant activities of the aqueous and ethanolic leaf extracts of life plant (*kalanchoe pinnata* l.) in the Niger Delta Nigeria. *Faculty of Natural and Applied Sciences Journal of Scientific Innovations*, 3(3), pp.1-10.
37. Predanócyová K, Šedík P. HONEY MARKET CHALLENGES: FLAVORED HONEY AS HEALTHY FOOD CHOICE FOR CONSUMERS. *Journal of microbiology, biotechnology and food sciences*. 2024 Apr 18;13(6): e11021-.
38. Long JM, Mohan A. Food flavoring prepared with lemon by - product. *Journal of Food Processing and Preservation*. 2021 Jun;45(6): e15462.

HOW TO CITE: Buddharatna Dongre*, Karan Sukalkar, Akshay Brokar, Dr. Akshit Naveriya, Preparation and Evaluation of *Kalanchoe pinnata* Herbal Tea for kidney stone treatment, *Int. J. of Pharm. Sci.*, 2025, Vol 3, Issue 6, 2794-2810. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15703308>

